

1 **DKFZP586I1420, a TE differentiation-associated product.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 DKFZP586I1420, a TE differentiation-associated product that has functions in lineage commitment in the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

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